

ASTROLOGY AND VAASTU ARE THE GUIDE FOR HOUSE BUILDING AND DESIGNING

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Abstract:

The astrology and vaastu help to predict one's ability to build/ own a house. And it's effects in his own life and his family members.

Key Words: Horoscope, vaastu, building, Planets, fourth house, bhava, lord, Directions, Main Door, North, South, East, West. , Four Corners, Indra, Agni, Yama, Nriti, Varuna, Vayu, Kubera, Esvara

Introduction:

Owning a nice home is a lifelong ambition for everyone, Peace and success does not just come from work, job, wealth, money, love and family it is also comes from the auspicious home, which is built as per horoscope and vaastu. A ordinary building is a building but when it is used by the family it becomes a home, In a home good things are happned only based on the horoscope of the head of the family and the vastu of the building.

The Importance of the Horoscope in Buildings:

If one's horoscope is not in good position, one will not get a house according to one's choice and desires. So according to me a horoscope is first and foremost important thing , Then vastu of buildings , If horoscope is not suitable for one to have a good house then vastu will not have a major role.

An Idea About to Have a Good House as per the Horoscope:

The fourth house of the horoscope and the sevvai (Mars) are the main factors to have a house, if the fourth house is afflicted, The person will not likely to get a good house and if Mars , The ruler of wealth and house , is Malefic in one's horoscope , It will also give bad results . The Person will not have a good auspicious home.

Guru, Sukkiran, Budan (Jubitor, Venus, Mercury):

If the above planets are in fourth house, or over viewing the fourth house, then surely he will have a nice, aesthetic, luxurious, good neighborhood house.

Sani, Raghu, Kethu (Saturn, Raghu, Kethu):

If the above planets are in the fourth house or over viewings the fourth house the fourth house will be afflicted , The person can't get a house , if he have a house that house will not be used by him,

The Role of Nine Planets in the Fourth House:

Sun: If the sun is well placed in the fourth house, the person will build his own house on his ancestral land, if he builds his own house on his ancestral land he will have an auspicious life.

Moon: If the Moon is well placed in the fourth house, The person will build his own house on his Mother land if he builds his own house on his Mother land he will have an auspicious life.

Mars: if Mars is in fourth house, the person will not be able to build his own house, relatives will hinder him from building his own house.

Mercury: if Mercury is in fourth house as in good position, the person will have a great support from his maternal uncle to construct his dream house and having auspicious life.

Jubitor: If jubitor is in fourth house, the person will build his own house on his self support and his self earned money, and the house will be big and people will appreciate him.

Venus: If venus is in the fourth house, The person will build his own house with the support of his wife, and the house will be in his wife name.

Saturn: If saturn is in the fourth house, There will be many hurdles and obstacles in the construction of one's own house .if he builds his own house it will be not to his satisfaction.

Rahu and Kethu: If Rahu and Kethu are in fourth house then the person is not likely to build his own house , if he build his own house he will not live in that house. Also the people in that house will suffer from many diseases.

Directions of the Main Door of the House:

- If the lord of fourth house is Sun then the main door should face the EAST directions,
- If the lord of the Fourth House is MOON then the main door shall face the SOUTH EAST,
- If the lord of the fourth house is MARS then the main door shall face SOUTH directions,
- If the lord of the fourth house is MERCURY then the main door shall face NORTH EAST directions.

- If the lord of the fourth house is JUBITOR then the main door shall face the NORTH directions.
- If the lord of the fourth house is VENUS then the main door shall face the EAST directions.
- If the lord of the fourth house is SATURN then the main door shall face the WEST directions,
- If the lord of the fourth house is VENUS then the main door shall face the EAST directions

How Directions are Effective in Giving Benefits:

Lords of Four Directions and Four Corners:

Our forefathers have regretted that. Its details are as follows: Lords are Indra to the East, Agni to the South East, Yama to the South, Nriti to the South West, Varuna to the West, Vayu to the North West, Kubera to the North and Isvara to the North East.

Benefits of East Direction:

A house facing the street in the east direction is called an east facing house. Residents of a house with an east-facing thalai (main) gate have the power to absorb the climatic conditions caused by wind, rain, heat etc. Indiran (lord) is the giver of this power. He is the king of the gods, rich; Gives good results like education, career excellence, peace, mental encouragement, well-being. Therefore, it is the view of the Manayadi (Vaastu) scriptures that those with east facing main door are eligible to enjoy the above auspicious benefits!

Benefits of South Direction:

If the street is on the south side of the house, it is called south facing house. The deity (Lord) belonging to this direction is Yama, the impartial justice. A fighter for integrity; He is morally wrong. Hence, a house with south facing "Main Door". The possessors are well-mannered and upright, and have good health as a breeze blows through the Main door. Any other diseases will be removed easily. Also, the residents of this house will have majestic appearance. He has the power to achieve what he sets his mind to. He is very interested in getting rich. But, they are likely to have more enemies.

Benefits of West Direction:

If the street is facing west and the door is facing west, it is called west facing house. Lord -Varuna belongs to the western direction. He is the lord of rain. He is the main reason why all crops flourish! Hence, the natives of this house will be very interested in farming. They are involved in long thought and deep research. The western wind is very hot and creates heat, hence the residents of this house are prone to heat related diseases. But, they are strong-minded and strong-willed.

Benefits of North Direction:

A house with the north facing street from the street is called a north facing house. lord -Kubera is the deity associated with this direction. Wealthy; Good at business; Meek; A master of all arts. Deka(Health) is weak. Therefore, the residents of this house are afraid of committing sins; Politician (or) Does not engage in public affairs but patiently attends to his own affairs. But those who love money. They even resort to wrong ways to earn money. As their health is often affected, they always have medicine on hand. North wind is sweet tasting and viscous in nature. Cool. Therefore, the residents of this house are likely to have "Sitala"- disease and " pithama". People with 'Kapham' disease. It is not good to live in this house.

Benefits of North East Direction:

A house with streets in the north and east is called a north-facing house. Isaan (Ishvara) is the deity associated with this. It is very good. Residents of this house excel in education and questions. They have virtues like penance, fame, divine grace, interest in arts, encouragement in research. However, they have a bit more temper; No one is easily trusted. He behaves according to his will. Wealth and prosperity will come to them automatically. The northeast wind tastes sweet. Delightful to the mind. Balances minerals in the body. Therefore, the residents of this house can live free from diseases such as splenomegaly, gallstones, gout etc. However, there is a possibility of eye disease and blood bile.

Benefits of South East Direction:

A house with streets in the east and south is called a southeast house. For this, the Main gate is in the east (a) south direction. Agni is the deity belonging to the south-east direction. Agni is purified. Easily angered. It can quickly destroy its surroundings. The navel region of our body is the seat of heat, which is the cause of homam, pukkam, etc., as well as rebellion, confusion, etc. Therefore, people living in this house are likely to get diseases related to stomach and kidney. Residents of a South-East facing house are more stubborn and easily emotional People, who like to be alone, cheat without guile. They will not hesitate to give their lives for the ones they love. However, they will try to eradicate the unwanted people. The residents of this house are poor and hardworking. Generally, it is not good to build a house in this corner. Women living in this house will experience poor health. The house will change hands. Dominance of the female progeny will prevail. As the southeast wind is very hot, the residents of this house are more prone to heat related diseases.

Benefits of South West Direction:

A house with streets in the south and west, It is called South West House. Its head is facing west (a) south direction. Lord Nriti is the deity belonging to the south-west direction. He is the leader of 'ASURA' clan. Low spirited. stubbornness, Authoritarian minded Hence, South West house occupants will be more interested in leadership positions. Those who behave spontaneously. Unpretentious, hardworking, and discontented. Winds

blowing from the south-west direction can cause diseases like "MEGA" disease and apathy. Also, it reduces the strength of the body. Therefore, it is better to avoid living in this house.

Benefits of North West Direction:

A house with streets in the north and west is called a north-west house. The Main gate of this house faces west or (a) north. Lord Vayu is the deity belonging to the north-west direction. A man of great strength; He who gives both good and evil. Therefore, they are determined in the North-West house: those who can endure oppositions are those who strive to save, those who have religious power are priests, therefore, Generally, it is good for advocates and judges to live in this house. Not so good for others. The west wind is (karpu), a bitter taste reduces the watery pithas in the body; Irritation, which causes them, Therefore, it is important to note that this villa is not suitable for people with vada, pithama, and thin DEGA (slim body)

If the Lord of Fourth House in Weak Position:

Then the strong and well placed planet which is associated with the lord of the fourth house will be taken for deciding the direction of the MAIN DOOR. If the lord of the fourth house is associated with the lord of rasi and in strong position, and there is no planet is associated with these planets, and jupiter and mars with four or five planets in this situation, we should not place the main door direction in the prescribed direction of the lord of fourth house. If they are not following this condition a compleing situaaion sill rise to sell the built house with in two years. DISA PUTHY in deciding the fate of the house, Even the lord of fourth house, MARS, Lord of lagna, lord of rasi and the strong association with the jupiter, we shall start the house construction in the dasa puthies of these planets then only the house will long lasting and gives so much pleasure and luxirious lifes. But if we start the house constructions in the dasa puthys of the malefic and adverse planets rhen we will have a very bad and bitter experiences from the newly built home, and some time the family members of the family will be affected by some co-morbids and cronical disesases. Even the newly built house had been constructed on the basis of the norms and rules of the VAASTU it won't give any prosperous and auspicious life while living in that house.

The Lord of Fourth Bhava:

- If the lord of the fourth bhava is afflicted and in 6-8-12 bavas, there will be no opportunity to build his own house, if he build his own house it will not give any benefit to him moreover he will not be using that house.
- If the Lord of fourth bhava and Mars are in good auspicious positions, the person will have a great house which will last for several decades and last to 100 years, and the inmates will have a prosperous life in all respects.
- If the lord of the fourth bhava is in good strength, and the mars is in debilitation, There will be ups and downs in his life in his own house.
- If the lord of the fourth bhava and Mars are in very bad, weak positions with adverse planets, the person will not be able to build his own house in his life time.
- Even the lord of the fourth bhava is in strong and well placed but does not having a contact with the jupiter and the lord of lagna , Then he will not be able to build/have his own house because of the lack of association with these jupiter and lord of lagna.
- If the Lord of lagna, jupiter, lord of rasi are not associated with the lord of fourth bava and Mars, Then the person can't build /have his own house.

Few Important Things to Consider When Starting Building a House:

- First of all, prepare the pit and make sure that there is no pit in the west.
- While digging the foundation, first start from the north-east and from there dig a trench towards north-west and then dig a trench from north-east towards south-east. Then, the trench should be dug from northwest direction to southwest direction. Finally, the trench should be dug from southwest to southeast and the southern side should be completed.
- When starting to build a house, one should start building from northwest to northeast and from southwest to southeast, i.e. from west to east and from south to north.
- Bricks, sand etc. stored for building houses should be stored in South (a) West. Do not store in East (a) North East!
- At the end of the work every day, lay some rows of bricks in the south west directions so that the south-west side is high and the north-east side is low.
- If renovating old houses or removing (a) old wall, start from north-east side and remove. Know that the bricks, stones etc. so demolished should be piled in south (a) west direction.
- House wall (a) Circular wall etc. should not be built in a curved shape in North-East. Better to build square corner.
- Before building a house, it is very good to build a compound. If this is done, Vastu 'doshas" related to neighboring house will not affect our site , Manayadi Shastra says that it will not attack in our site

- If the house is constructed in violation of the above conditions, there will be many obstacles (a) delay in the completion of the house work. Head of Household (a) someone in the family may suffer from health problems. It may also bring poverty, debt, business failure, enemy harassment, etc.! Need attention!!
- Method of doing puja before building a house

It is very important to do Bhoomi Puja before building a house. On an auspicious day, after worshipping Lord Ganesha, Durga, etc.

Conclusion:

Based on some of the above findings one can predict the life of one's life in according to the buildings in one's own house. So, If a person start to thik about to have a dream home, first he has to get the blessing of his kula thiyam " The god of his family) and from the the ISTA THEIVAM (the lord of his desires), Then he has to consult a good, genuine astrologer who is having faith in god and in astrology, and following the prescribed rituals, and rules in astrology. Then he has to approach a good genuine VAASTU consultant, and after these with the help of the astrologer he has to find the position of planets and the status of his horoscope, and analysis the dasa puthys, and opt time in astrology, and with the help of the vaastu consultant he has to finalize the positions of rooms, and directions of the main door, and finalize the dimentions of the proposed house. Then with the help of an ARCHITECT, Building engineer, build the dream home.

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